

DECODING QUANTUM, DECODING THE UNIVERSE

Part 6. The origin of the Moon, the Universe is revealing all mysteries.

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Abstract.

Based on archaeological data, combining Quantum codes, physical analysis of celestial bodies, connect all evidence in the Solar System, we have calculated and discovered the origin of the Moon.

Decoding Quantum, decoding the Universe.

QUANTUM are perfect physical entities, have the power to operate the Universe, are the source of all movement. Quantum create all matter, planets, life,... and the majestic Universe.

Nice Earth, be ready to receive the “QUANTUM CODE”, is the key to decode all the mysteries of science, upgrade science and technology to the Quantum level.

Quantum is the origin of everything and all physical phenomena, combine with deep physics thinking, will solve all the problems of science, and invent many technologies to make life better.

Holding the Quantum code, nothing is mysterious anymore.

This scientific work has 8 parts, see details of each part in the separate publication. After scientific community review and confirmation, the entire Quantum code will be published fully. Now, details of part 6 will be published first.

1. INTRODUCTION.

Part 1. Quantum decoding, is the key to decode all the mysteries of science.

QUANTUM is the origin of everything and all physical phenomena, combine with deep physics thinking, will solve all the problems of science, and invent many technologies to make life better.

Part 2. Earth and Solar System are formed and operated by Quantum.

Based on archaeological data, combining Quantum codes, physical analysis of celestial bodies, connect all evidence on the entire Earth, we have calculated and discovered the origin of Earth and the Solar System.

Part 3. TRANZERAR is origin of the Universe, locate it by a device.

Analyzing observed data in the area of 93 billion light years, combine with Quantum structure, we have discovered that the Universe is formed and operated according to Quantum laws, and invent a device to detect the Tranzerar.

Part 4. Quantum cycle of the Universe, answers the age, beginning, end point and limit of the Universe.

Quantum will let us know the Universe operates according to the Quantum cycle, and will know the limit of the Universe. Analyzing the operation of celestial bodies, will calculate the age of each part of the Universe.

Part 5. The Earth is operated by Quantum, analysis to determine the natural disasters impending.

After studying parts 1-2-3-4, now we have understood everything:

Understanding the Earth operated by Quantum, will know the origin of natural disasters such as volcanoes, earthquakes, tsunamis..., so will determine the time and extent it occurs, will prevent, reduce damage a lot.

Part 6. The origin of the Moon, the Universe is revealing all mysteries.

Based on archaeological data, combining Quantum codes, physical analysis of celestial bodies, connect all evidence in the Solar System, we have calculated and discovered the origin of the Moon.

Part 7. Laws and constants of quantum physics.

Some laws and constants of physics to confirm and popularize knowledge about quantum physics. See details in the parts that will be published.

Part 8. Scientific inventions based on Quantum code.

Some scientific inventions and new technology, especially important that you are about to receive, will make life better.

2. CONTENT.

Part 6. The origin of the Moon, the Universe is revealing all mysteries.

Based on archaeological data, combining Quantum codes, physical analysis of celestial bodies, connect all evidence in the Solar System, we have calculated and discovered the origin of the Moon.

1. The process of the Moon being locked in motion with the Earth.

Based on evidence, analyze and calculate velocities, distances, forces, etc., we know exactly the process of the Moon being locked in motion. Based on archaeological data, shows that it happened about 53 million years ago, the details as follows:

1.1. Geological analysis of the gray areas on the Moon and the Southeast Asian region on Earth, we see a match as follows:

a. The entire gray area on the Moon is a bedrock of solid basalt, 5-8km deep, see many meteorite craters, but the Regolith dust, rocks and soil have disappeared.

A circular area, 1200km wide and 5-8km deep, surrounded by mountain ranges, with traces of being cut by flowing water, direction from the center outwards. This circle has a 650km wide clean zone, extending more than 2000km outwards.

b. On Earth, the Southeast Asian region appears in the ocean, not a tectonic plate, it has a geological structure that is completely different from the rest of the Earth, with an area in the ocean of 2800x4200km, nearly as the size of the gray area of the Moon.

It has the volcanic belt and Regolith dust belt surrounding, extends across the equator at 26.5 degrees, matching the Moon's angle to Earth of 18.5-28.5 degrees. This Regolith dust is a characteristic type of lunar dust that Apollo collected samples of.

1.2. Notice all the matches, and it is exactly as calculated in physics as follows:

a. Before that, the Moon was in orbit between Venus and Earth, with a higher velocity than Earth, as its orbit approaches, it was pulled in by gravity, and a collision occurred in Southeast Asia (at that time, it was the ocean).

b. Combining velocity, inertia, and the two spheres, causes the Moon to roll on the Earth about 2400km in 4 minutes. Then, inertia causes it to leave the Earth, while gravity continuously pulls it back. Finally, this creates a lock on the Moon's motion. (All is calculated using physics).

- c. The collision and rolling cracked the Earth's surface, forming the Southeast Asian volcanic belt, extends across the equator at 26.5 degrees. At the same time, Regolith dust fell, forming a thick layer along the belt.
- d. At its final point, upon leaving Earth, it left behind a crater, 500 km wide, which is the Banda Sea today.

- e. Strong gravitational force of Earth has pull down all soil, rocks and Regolith dust on the Moon's collision and rolling zone, only remain the bedrock of solid basalt that look gray color. Estimated this amount of soil, rocks and Regolith dust is equal to the area of Southeast Asia in the ocean.

1.3. Time of collision, based on a lot of data and evidence as follow:

- a. The Regolith dust belt in Southeast Asia was formed 52-53 million years ago.
- b. The thin layer of Regolith dust, on the gray areas of the Moon, is 52-53 million years old, it was sampled by Apollo.

c. Marine fossils have been found on continents and high mountains near Southeast Asia, are 50-54 million years old, now we have evidence of its origin. The cause is that the collision on the ocean pushed a lot of water and marine life up there.

d. Earth's temperature is rising abnormally around 53-56 million years ago.

2. The Moon is Earth's younger sibling.

Based on parts 2 and 3, the Moon was born from the Sun, similar to Earth.

Based on NASA data, the age of lunar rocks is younger than that of Earth by 30 million years.

3. The Universe is revealing all mysteries.

Anyone who can apply Quantum code, combine with deep physical thinking, will be able to decode all mysteries and explain all phenomena in the Universe using real physics, without needing abstract hypotheses anymore.

4. Conclusion.

Much of the physics data and new discoveries above, scientific community can verify the facts.

See the next part in the separate publication.

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Send email, I will decode all the mysteries of science.

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